

Vanadium Dioxide base Picosecond Electromagnetic Pulse Generator

N.A. Charipar, H. Kim, S. A. Mathews, and A. Piqué

Naval Research Laboratory, 4555 Overlook Ave, SW, Washington DC 20375, USA
nicholas.charipar@nrl.navy.mil

Abstract We investigate the use of thin film VO₂ as a fast-switching material for use in photoconductive emitters. These emitters rely on the semiconductor-metal transition in VO₂ to generate ultrafast electrical pulses.

1. Introduction

Femtosecond lasers have led to the development and characterization of ultrafast electrical devices such as the photoconductive switch [1]. These switches typically consist of two metallic contacts separated by a high resistivity photoconductive material. Upon illumination, photo carriers are generated, resulting in a rapid increase in conductivity. Low-temperature GaAs (LT-GaAs) has been the canonical material for ultrafast electrical pulse generation because of its ideal properties such as low dark current, high carrier mobility, and short recombination times. We investigate VO₂ as an alternative material for ultrafast devices. This material exhibits a semiconductor-to-metal transition (SMT) at ≈ 68 °C [2]. This transition can be induced thermally, electrically, or optically [3], resulting in a change of resistance of over four orders of magnitude. The change in resistivity is due to the dramatic increase in carrier density ($\sim 10^{19}$ - 10^{23} cm⁻³), rather than photo carrier generation as is the case with LT-GaAs. While VO₂ may appear less than ideal due to its low carrier mobility (~ 0.1 cm²/V-s) and long recovery times (\approx ns), femtosecond laser pulses can induce the SMT with sub-picosecond rise times.

2. Fabrication

VO₂ thin films were deposited by pulsed laser deposition (PLD) on c-axis, single crystal sapphire substrates. The growth conditions and characterization details have been previously reported [4]. The films had a thickness of 120 nm and exhibited a change in resistivity of 4 orders of magnitude upon transition. The temperature dependent resistivity and X-ray diffraction (XRD) data are displayed in figure 1(a). The coplanar strips (CPS) used to DC bias the dipole were 200 nm thick and fabricated via conventional photolithography. The gold strips were 20 μ m wide and were separated by a 50 μ m gap. A coax cable was attached to the ends of the CPS using silver paste.

Figure 1. a) XRD pattern of one of the VO₂ films grown on c-axis Al₂O₃ single crystal substrates. The peaks at 41.7° and 90.8° are indexed to the (0006) and (00012) planes of the c-Al₂O₃ substrate. The peaks at 39.9° and 85.9° are indexed to the (020) and (040) planes of monoclinic VO₂, respectively. The resistivity of the sample drops by more than 4 orders of magnitude with increased temperature, as seen in the inset of figure 1, and demonstrates a clear SMT transition in the VO₂ at a temperature consistent with the known transition temperature [2]. b) Optical micrograph of fabricated device.

3. Results

The devices were DC biased with an external current limiting resistor and optically excited at 1030 nm using a femtosecond laser as shown schematically in figure 2(a). The laser pulse duration was measured to be 280 fs using a single shot optical correlator. A commercial GaBiAs photoconductive antenna was used as the detector. The detector signal was amplified using a low-noise, high gain current amplifier and digitized using a lock-in amplifier. The time dependent electric field measurements are shown in figure 2(b).

Figure 2. a) Device characterization schematic. b) Measured time dependent electric field

The primary pulse at 7ps has a FWHM of 1.2ps while the secondary pulse at 12ps has a FWHM of 1.8ps. The additional structure in the waveform after the primary pulse is due to the slow recovery time of VO₂, thereby enabling multiple reflections and various modes. This device demonstrates that it is possible to generate picosecond pulses by exploiting the semiconductor-metal transition in VO₂. The semiconductor to metal transition mechanism is distinctly different from the photocarrier generation process used by conventional devices. While this device exhibits a short initial pulse, additional designs should be considered to either take advantage of or to mitigate the effects of the slow recovery time of VO₂. One possibility to capitalize on the slow recovery time would be to build a highly resonant structure to generate millimeter or submillimeter wave bursts. Another option would be mitigation of the multiple reflections via better impedance matching, introducing resistive/dielectric losses or dispersion.

In conclusion VO₂ based picosecond electromagnetic pulse generators were fabricated and characterized. The devices were capable of generating ~1.2ps FWHM pulses when excited with a 280 fs laser pulse, indicating that sub-picosecond pulses could be generated by using shorter laser pulses (< 100 fs). These results demonstrate that the semiconductor-to-metal transition can be used as a fast switching material for electrical pulse generation.

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References

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